

Conductometric Study of Some Metal Complexes with Picrolonic Acid

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Conductometric study confirms the complex formation by picrolonic acid with Tl(I) in the ratio of 1:1; with Ca, Ba, Sr, Co, Ni, Mn, Zn, Fe, Cu, Pb and Cd (all bivalent) in the ratio of 1:2; and with Ce(IV), and Th(IV), in the ratio of 1:4.

Gravimetric studies by various workers of the complexes of alkaline earth metals, thallium, zinc, copper, manganese, cobalt, and lead salts with picrolonic acid have been mentioned in our previous communication¹. Besides these, picrolonic acid has been reported as a quantitative precipitant for Th(IV)² as $\text{Th}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_3)_4$ and a microchemical reagent for Fe(II)³, etc. The present investigation deals with the conductometric study of mixtures of picrolonic acid with fourteen metal salts to confirm their compositions. Fe(II) forms a black precipitate, but other metals form yellow ones with picrolonic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\text{Tl}_2(\text{SO}_4)$, CaCO_3 , $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$, and $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality. A definite amount of acetic acid was added in CaCO_3 and sulphuric acid in ferrous ammonium sulphate to prepare the standard solutions. The reagent, picrolonic acid, was of EKC (Eastman Kodak, U.S.A.) chemically pure quality.

The experimental set up was the same as in our previous communication¹.

The reaction was studied by Job's method⁴ of continued variations for measurements of conductance of the supernatant liquid. Monovariation method⁵ was also applied in those cases (Ca, Sr, Ni, Fe, Cd, Ce, and Th) to which it was not applied previously¹. The total volume of the mixture was kept at 12 ml in both the methods and the measurement was made in each case after keeping the mixed solutions overnight. A large number of observations were taken, some of which were plotted. The relevant data are summarised in Tables I and II (different metals have been grouped together to economise space). In the tables c represents the concentration of the metal solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of picrolonic acid solution).

1. Joshi and Jain, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 241, 242.

2. Dupuis and Duval, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 3, 589.

3. Berisso, *Chem. Abs.*, 1946, 40, 6016.

4. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

5. Nayar and Pande, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 27A, 284.

TABLE I

Job's method (equimolar and non-equimolar).

Salts.	$c \times 10^{-3} M$.	p .	Vol. at the peak.	Composition of the complex.	Salts.	$c \times 10^{-3} M$.	p .	Vol. at the peak.	Composition of the complex.	
Thallous sulphate	3.33	1.00	6.0 ml	1 : 1	Barium chloride	6.35	0.40	2.0	1 : 2	
	2.50	1.00	6.0	1 : 1		3.75	0.68	3.0	1 : 2	
	2.00	1.00	6.0	1 : 1		Nickel sulphate	3.33	1.00	4.0	1 : 2
	13.33	0.25	2.4	1 : 1			2.50	1.00	4.0	1 : 2
	10.00	0.33	3.0	1 : 1			6.66	0.50	2.4	1 : 2
Strontium chloride	2.50	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	Manganese sulphate	5.00	0.50	2.4	1 : 2	
	2.00	1.00	4.0	1 : 2		4.00	0.50	2.4	1 : 2	
	5.00	0.40	2.0	1 : 2		Ferrous ammonium sulphate	2.00	1.00	4.0	1 : 2
3.00	0.68	3.0	1 : 2	1.66	1.00		4.0	1 : 2		
Calcium acetate	1.00	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	1.00		1.00	4.0	1 : 2	
	0.80	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	5.00		0.50	2.4	1 : 2	
	0.66	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	Zinc sulphate		4.00	0.50	2.4	1 : 2
2.00	0.50	2.4	1 : 2	5.00		0.40	2.0	1 : 2		
Copper sulphate	1.60	0.50	2.4	1 : 2		Ceric ammonium nitrate	3.33	1.00	2.4	1 : 4
	1.33	0.50	2.4	1 : 2	2.50		1.00	2.4	1 : 4	
Cadmium sulphate	2.50	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	2.00		1.00	2.4	1 : 4	
	2.00	1.00	4.0	1 : 2	Thorium nitrate		1.66	2.00	4.0	1 : 4
Cobalt sulphate	1.00	1.00	4.0	1 : 2		1.25	2.00	4.0	1 : 4	
						1.00	2.00	4.0	1 : 4	

TABLE II

Monovariation method (direct and reverse titrations).

Fig. No.	Curves No.	Salts.	$c \times 10^{-3} M$.	P.	Fixed vol. (ml).	Vol. at inflection (ml)	Composition of the complex.	Fig. No.	Curves No.	Salts.	$c \times 10^{-3} M$.	P.	Fixed vol. (ml).	Vol. at inflection (ml).	Composition of the complex.		
8	A & A ₁	Cadmium sulphate	2.50	1.00	3.0 metal each in A & B	6.0 in A & B	1 : 2	10	A & A ₁	Calcium	C.80	1.00	As in Fig.8	As in Fig.8	1 : 2		
	C & C ₁								acetate	2.00						0.50	1 : 2
	B & B ₁								Strontium chloride	2.00						1.00	6.0 reagent each in A & B
9	C & C ₁	Nickel sulphate	4.00	0.50	1.0 metal in A & B	4.0 in C	1 : 2	11	C & C ₁	Carrie ammonium nitrate	1.66	2.00	3.0 reagent in B ₁	2.3 in B ₁ 3.0 in C ₁	1 : 4 1 : 4		
	A & A ₁								Ferrous ammonium sulphate	3.33						1.00	3.0 metal in C

N. B. Figures omitted to economise space.

DISCUSSION

Stability of the Complexes.—The data in the tables show that the maximum or inflection, both in equimolecular as well as in non-equimolecular solutions, has been obtained at the stoichiometric ratio, without having any shift due to dissociation. This indicates that the complexes are very stable and the reactions may be quantitative. Some of the metal complexes, mentioned earlier^{1,2}, have already been studied gravimetrically and rest are under investigation.

Structure of the Complexes.—As already reported¹, the reactions between metals and picrolonic acid may be represented by the equations:

Picrolonic acid exists in two tautomeric forms:

It is the labile H atom in (I) which is replaced by metal atoms.

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